

Comparison of Different Cloud Storage Services: A Study

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Abstract: The cloud service provider provides various services including backup, file sync, file storage, downloading, streaming, etc. Apart from this, the cloud service provider provides the best encryption service to its users. This paper compared 6 cloud providers serving the cloud; that name as Google Drive, Media Fire, pCloud, Microsoft One Drive, MEGA, and Amazon Drive. The MEGA cloud provides maximum free storage capacity up to 20GB. Shows cloud photos, video streaming, documents, etc., other than Amazon Drive. Also, Media Fire doesn't run video in the cloud.

Key Words: Cloud, Drive, Cloud storage, Cloud Name.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud provides its users with virtual storage similar to physical storage. As a result of the increase in accuracy, necessity, and clarity of information and data, today information has started to be made in MB instead of KB. The result can be seen clearly by zooming. At the same time, the main reason for the increasing use of the Internet is also responsible. According to **Dlgnan, Larry. (2021)**. today people are exchanging their study material, research documents, business-related files in e-format and the use of online software and apps have also increased such as Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, WebEx (for study and webinar), E-mail, WhatsApp, Telegram (for communication), Online games, IoT, etc. Cloud storage is an online data storage service. The provides its users free and paid secure storage capacity of their data like audio, video, photos, documents, etc. within certain storage limits. In which its users choose the cloud service provider according to their need from different cloud storage. That allows them to back up, Security, and Downloading their data. Some of these cloud storage providers are Google Drive, Amazon Drive, pCloud, Dropbox, Mega, IBM Cloud, Media Fire, and Microsoft One Drive.

1.1. What is Cloud Storage?

Cloud storage is a model of storing data based on the Internet. In which free and paid data storage is allowed by different vendors. Its users can store, download, share, view, etc. services like photos, files, videos, many more. Plus, they can be viewed and downloaded at anytime from anywhere in the world. These are including Google Drive, Media Fire, pCloud, Microsoft One Drive, MEGA, Amazon Drive, Dropbox, IMB Cloud, etc. Cloud storage is a type of data storage in which users store data on third-party online instead of offline (such as mobile, CD, pen drive, computer, or laptop). Hence the store of data that can be retrieved from anywhere in the world is called cloud storage.

1.2. Cloud storage service Provider:

Google Drive

Google Drive is the web version of Google. It is a file hosting type of service. Google Drive Pro. (n.d.). Define; the registration is required to use it. The service was launched on 24 April 2012. It currently offers free storage capacity and storage usage up to 15GB to its users. These include videos, PDFs, Google Docs, photos, etc. Futures:

- Files can be edited in Google drive such as Google spreadsheet, Google Docs, etc.
- Services can be accessed across multiple devices from the same account. Like Windows, Android, etc.
- Its free storage capacity is given up to 15GB. That is, the user can store his data up to 15GB.
- It manages various files automatically.
- It allows SSL encryption standards for security.²

(<https://drive.google.com>)

Media Fire

Media Fire Cloud Storage is a file storage service. According to **Wikipedia.(n.d.)**. It was founded in 2016 by Derek Labian and Tom Langridge. According to **Selmeczy, Peter.(2016, January 25)**. Media Fire is currently offers a

direct free file storage capacity of 10GB. In addition, Media Fire enlarges the storage capacity to 50GB for tasks such as installing on mobile and connecting to a Face book account.

Features:

- It offers file storage capacity ranging from 10GB to 50GB.
- It has provided a facility to drag files as well as folders.
- It uploads a Multi-file in one go.
- It provides unlimited bandwidth and downloading facility.

(<https://www.mediafire.com>)

pCloud

According to **Wikipedia.(n.d.)**, pCloud was founded in the year 2013 at Switzerland. pCloud provides both individual and business services. It also provides a high level of security to protect multiple TEDAs.

Features:

- It allows four family members to share cloud storage.
- It provides a lifetime plan to its users.
- An off-line retrieval facility is provided on their own device.
- It provides a facility for unlimited file upload and download.

(<https://www.pCloud.com>)

Microsoft One Drive

Microsoft.(n.d.). Define; Microsoft One Drive is a file hosting service. That was launched in the year 2007. That is powered by Microsoft. In which the user can register and store free up to 5GB of data. It can also share data.

Features:

- It provides a personal vault to save personal files.
- It allows offline file downloading. It used in Windows 8.1 and Windows 10.
- The file can be easily dragged and placed in the destination.
- It allows you to link and share large files.

(<https://www.microsoft.com/en-in/microsoft-365/onedrive/online-cloud-storage>)

Amazon Drive

According to **Wikipedia.(n.d.)**, Amazon Drive is a cloud storage application. That was first begun on March 24, 2011. When cloud storage was started in June 2017. That includes 5GB of cloud storage. Also, the web version of Amazon Drive does not offer automatic backup but the mobile version supports automatic backup.

Features:

- Since this service is offered in many countries, it is found to be multi linguistic.
- It facilitates the drag and drop of files on the cloud.
- It allows users to store unlimited photos.

(<https://www.amazon.com/CloudDrive>)

Mega

According to **Wikipedia.(n.d.)**. It is a cloud storage and file hosting services. That is provided by Mega Limited. It was launched in the year 2013. In which its user is given free storage capacity of up to 20GB. Also, Mega Cloud offers bonus storage for 365 days. These include tasks such as installing software on desktop and mobile applications.

Features:

- It shares the link of any file and allows you to download it. It does not require registration or signing in for download files.
- It provides a drag and drop facility.
- It provides the streaming facility on Cloud and users can be watching videos on the cloud. (<https://mega.io>)

2. OBJECTIVES :

- To study the availability of free storage capacity on the cloud.
- To study the various feature of cloud services.
- To study the uses of supported OS and types of files on the Cloud.

3. METHODOLOGY:

In this study, there have been attempts to select the best 6 clouds and it has been compared. The present study has focused on the features of Cloud storage providers. The Data is collected by exploring the cloud service provider through the website and analyzed using MS Excel in the month of March 2022.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING :

Tabel-1 Year wise Distribution

Sr. No.	Cloud name	Year	Registration	URL of Cloud
1	Google Drive	2012	YES	https://drive.google.com
2	Media Fire	2016	YES	https://www.mediafire.com
3	PCloud	2013	YES	https://www.pCloud.com
4	Microsoft One Drive	2007	YES	https://www.microsoft.com/en-in/microsoft-365/onedrive/online-cloud-storage
5	Amazon Drive	2011	YES	https://www.amazon.com/CloudDrive
6	MEGA	2013	YES	https://mega.io

Table 1 show that the first Microsoft one drive was beginning. Also, to get all the cloud services, it is necessary to register first.

Table-2 Availability of Free Storage capacity

Sr. No.	Cloud Name	Storage Capacity(GB)
1	Google Drive	15
2	Media Fire	10
3	pCloud	10
4	Microsoft OneDrive	5
5	Amazon Drive	5
6	MEGA	20

Table-2 and figure-1 show the capabilities of free cloud storage, with MEGA Cloud offering a maximum data storage capacity of up to 20GB. While Microsoft One Drive and Amazon Drive offer a minimum data storage capacity of up to 5GB.

Table-3 Provide features of cloud services

Cloud Name	Sharing Files	Sync Files	Uploading /Downloading File	Backup	Edit File
Google Drive	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Media Fire	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Pcloud	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Microsoft OneDrive	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Amazon Drive	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
MEGA	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Table 3 shows that the cloud provides all the features including such as sharing files, syncing files, uploading/downloading files, backing up, and editing files.

Table-4 Supported OS of Cloud Services

Cloud Name	Operating System				
	Android	Windows	Linux	Mac OS	iOS
Google Drive	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Media Fire	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Pcloud	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Microsoft OneDrive	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Amazon Drive	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
MEGA	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Table 4 shows that all cloud supports Android, Windows, Linux, MacOS, and iOS operating systems.

Table-5 Types of file show in cloud

Cloud Name	Files(like Excel, PowerPoint, PDF etc.
Google Drive	Any type of file can store in the cloud.
Media Fire	Any type of file can store in the cloud.
Pcloud	Any type of file can store in the cloud.
Microsoft OneDrive	Any type of file can store in the cloud.
Amazon Drive	It can store only Photos and video types on the cloud.
MEGA	Any type of file can store in the cloud.

Table-5 shows that Amazon Drive stores only photos and videos type files, while the rest of the cloud stores Google Drive, Media Fire, pCloud, Microsoft one drive, and MEGA store all file types in the cloud.

Table-6 Availability of video streaming facility

Cloud Name	Video Streaming
Google Drive	YES
Media Fire	NO
Pcloud	YES
Microsoft OneDrive	YES
Amazon Drive	YES
MEGA	YES

Table-6 shows that Google Drive, pCloud, Microsoft One Drive, Amazon Drive, and MEGA are providing video streaming facilities. While the Media Fire does not provide that facility.

5. FINDING :

- Registrations are required in all cloud services. This means that the user who wants to get cloud service has to register first in that cloud.
- MEGA Cloud provides the cloud with a maximum free storage capacity of up to 20GB.
- All Cloud supports android, windows, Linux, MacOS, and iOS operating systems.
- Google Drive, Media Fire, pCloud, Microsoft one drive, and MEGA show all types of files in the cloud.
- The Media Fire does not show video streaming.

6. CONCLUSION:

It is considered to save with the emergence of data. Today, data has grown so much in e-form that it cannot be stored on your mobile or storage device. Also sometimes due to various viruses the data file gets corrupted or the mobile hangs and the data cannot be viewed in time. Thus different cloud storage solves your problem. It has some free cloud storage in which users can store data up to 25GB to 50GB more data (by installing a mobile app and with social media login). In this research, there has been a comparison of different cloud storage providers. They are all very useful and most used by users.

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